

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRE-MARITAL EXAMINATIONS

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Abstract: *The aim of the current study is, the importance of pre-marital examination, the importance of tests taken for both spouses, the role of these tests in keeping future generations free from serious hereditary diseases. , the questionnaire was created electronically via the Google Drive program, and then it was distributed via mobile phone on the social networking program (WhatsApp)? Using e-mail for all participants to respond to the questionnaire. 500 questionnaires were distributed to all mobile groups, and 550 questionnaires were received on the researcher's e-mail. (The target group is residents of the holy city of Mecca, aged 25-60 years).*

Keywords: *importance of pre-marital examinations*

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Please cite this article in press *Mazen.G. Saeedi et al., The Importance Of Pre-Marital Examinations., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2023; 10 (12).*

1-INTRODUCTION:

Premarital medical examination is a set of comprehensive medical tests for the purpose of determining whether individuals about to marry have diseases such as hereditary blood diseases and infectious diseases. Statistically, one out of every 25 children are affected by either a hereditary disease, a birth defect, or a mental retardation resulting from a genetic defect or a disease that has genetic factors ⁽¹⁾. The medical examination reveals the presence of any hereditary or infectious diseases, and the examinations vary according to the gender and kinship of the spouses ⁽²⁾. Pre-marital medical examination for non-relatives' men: Tests include blood type determination, blood factor, hemoglobin level, blood sugar level, hepatitis B virus, AIDS, syphilis analysis and semen analysis. Women: A test for the German measles virus and hormones: estrogen and progesterone are added to men's tests. Pre-marital medical examination of relative's men: the same tests for relatives in addition to thalassemia and chromosomal examination. Women: The same tests as for relatives, in addition to thalassemia and chromosomal examination. Premarital screening is defined as testing couples who are planning to get married soon for common genetic blood disorders (e.g. sickle cell anemia and thalassemia and sickle cell anemia) and infectious diseases (e.g. hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and HIV/AIDS). For couples that are about to get married, pre-marital screening helps detect potential health problems and risks for themselves and also their offspring. It is very important for couples to be screened in order to help them understand their genetics and help them take the necessary precautions or treatments. It is one of the most important strategies for prevention of genetic disorders, congenital abnormalities and several medical, psychosocial marital problems. It also provides an opportunity of intervention including vaccination, genetic and behavioral counselling, guidance regarding contraception, medical treatment for infections or chronic diseases, and medication to decrease risks based upon identified disease, risks or anomalies. In addition to early detection, prevention and treatment of diseases or abnormalities, premarital screening and interventions have been found to be effective in different ways such as in improving interpersonal skills and overall relationship quality, decreasing risk factors such as poor communication skills for later marital problems and increasing the quality of life for couples and families who stay together. Premarital counselling is also generally acceptable because of its minimal cost and health requirements. Premarital screening includes routine investigations such as Complete Blood Count (CBC), Complete Urine Analysis and Peripheral Blood

Smears to check for normal and abnormal cells, Blood group testing (ABO-RH), Infectious diseases testing such as Syphilis, HI, Hepatitis-B and C Virus testing and Genetic testing such as Thalassemia. This quantitative study explores the awareness and importance of premarital screening among young adults planning to get married soon and aims to develop insights regarding the type of screening tests to be included in the premarital screening based on their responses. This article also explores the need for premarital counselling among young adults and the time duration when such tests and counselling can be undertaken ⁽³⁾. As early as 1913, many States had passed laws regarding premarital physical examination. While these differed from State, none of them was particularly effective. A medical certificate of freedom from venereal disease on the part of the male applicant was all that was required to secure a marriage license in Alabama, North Dakota, Oregon, and Wisconsin. In New York and Pennsylvania, both applicants were required to state under oath that they were free from venereal disease and tuberculosis. Indiana, Michigan, New Jersey, Oklahoma, and Vermont had regulations making it a misdemeanor for a person having a venereal disease to marry, but there were no adequate enforcement measures or any penalties for noncompliance. The Utah law provided that a marriage between persons afflicted with a venereal disease was void. The Virginia law provided that if the woman was under 45 years of age, the man must swear that he was free from any contagious venereal disease and he also must make an affidavit that he believed the woman named in the license to marry was free from such disease. Early in 1918, there was renewed interest in legislation for protection of family life. This interest centered around providing uniform marriage laws and physical examinations for both parties to the marriage. By 1925, a great number of States had adopted general legislation intended to safeguard marriage partners from venereal disease. After 1925, however, the campaign against venereal disease slowed down. There was little enforcement of the laws, and practically no new legislation was introduced in the States.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study started in (the holy city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), began writing the research and then recording the questionnaire in June 2023, and the study ended with data collection in October 2023. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the social phenomenon (The importance of pre-marital examinations). This kind of study is characterized by analysis, reason, objectivity, and reality, as it is concerned with individuals and societies, as it studies

the variables and their effects on the health of the individual, society, and consumer, the spread of diseases and their relationship to demographic variables such as age, gender, nationality, and marital status. Status, occupation ⁽⁴⁾, And use the Excel 2010 Office suite histogram to arrange the results using: Frequency tables Percentages ⁽⁵⁾. A questionnaire is a remarkable and helpful tool for collecting a huge amount of data, however, researchers were not able to personally interview participants on the online survey, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent infection between participants and researchers and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only answered the questionnaire electronically, because the questionnaire consisted of eight questions, all of which were closed. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere ⁽⁶⁾

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The percentage of participants in a questionnaire examining the importance of premarital examinations was 100%, and the percentage of participants' ages was as follows: from the age of 25-34 years (12.5%), from the age of 35-44 years 75%, and from the age of 45-55 years 12.5%. As for Participants in the questionnaire were as follows: The percentage of females was 12.5% and the percentage of males was 87.5%. All participants were 100% Saudis, and their occupations were all 100% government employees,

while the educational status was as follows: primary 0%, middle school 0%, secondary school 0%. %, university 62.5%, master's 25%, doctorate 12.5%. As for the questions of the research questionnaire and the responses to them by the participants, they were as follows: The first question about a healthy marriage is a state of harmony and excellence between spouses in terms of health, psychological, physical, social, and awareness. The necessity of a healthy family and having healthy children? Yes 100% and no 0%. The second question about pre-marital medical examination is a procedure to examine those about to marry to determine the presence of genetic diseases such as sickle cell anemia, thalassemia, and some infectious diseases? Yes 100% and no 0%. The third question: What is the aim of the examination to spread awareness of the concept of a comprehensive, healthy marriage? Yes 100% and no 0%. The fourth question is about - One of the goals of the examination is to reduce pressure on health institutions and blood banks? Yes 100% and no 0%. The fifth question: Are there specialized centers for pre-marital examinations? Yes 87.5% and no 12.5%. The sixth question: What diseases does the pre-marital examination detect (hepatitis, AIDS, sickle cell anemia or thalassemia)? Yes 100% and no 0%. The seventh question: Are there conditions for pre-marital examinations? Yes 50% and no 50%. The last question is: Are the tests comprehensive for Saudis and non-Saudis? Yes 100% and no 0%. (Figure No.1).

Figure .No.1: The importance of pre-marital examinations for participants

4-CONCLUSION:

The importance of pre-marital examinations for society because it protects them from incurable diseases and serious diseases such as AIDS and hepatitis

Acknowledgment:

To start with, I would like to Praise God and thank Dr. Anas S. Dabloom, from Umm Al-Qura University (Public Health Department, Faculty of Health Sciences Al-leeth), Mecca, Saudi Arabia. And the researchers who make the project come to light.

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